

A STUDY ON CONSUMER'S BRAND PREFERENCE OF WASHING SOAP IN MAYILADUTHURAI TOWN

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ABSTRACT

Consumer is the person who actually uses a product. Thus, it becomes clear that a buyer need not be a consumer and a consumer also need not necessarily be a buyer. A buyer or a consumer becomes a customer if he regularly buys or consumes a product or service. As the market for consumer products is a highly competitive one, lack of knowledge of the behavior of buyers would enable the competitors to attract the consumer's attention towards their products. The brand preference of washing soap by the consumers can be satisfied only by offering products that fulfill their desires. The general belief is that good quality products at a reasonable price would positively influence the buyer behavior.

Key words: Customer behavior, Consumer research, Washing soaps, Consumer satisfaction, consumer awareness.

INTRODUCTION

Marketing is the process of communicating the value of a product or service to customers, for the purpose of selling the product or service. Marketing can be looked at as an organizational function and a set of processes for creating, delivering and communicating value to customers, and managing customer relationships in ways that also benefit the organization and its shareholders includes capturing marketing insight, connecting with customers, building strong brands. A brand is a name, term, symbol or design or a combination of these which is intended to identify the goods and services of one seller and to differentiate them from those of competitors.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The aim of marketing is to meet and satisfy targeted consumers needs that want perceptions, preferences and there by influencing the shopping and buying behaviour. Consumer preference varies from brand to brand on the basis of quality, price and advertisement etc. Consumer preference also varies with their income, age, sex and other characteristics. There are so many brands of soap available in the market i.e., Rin, power, Arasan, wheel, surf excel, Tide, Henko, Mr.white, Oorvasi, Ponvandu. The study covers all these brands of washing soaps. The research work has been carried out to know why these washing soap are preferred by the consumers. This study would bring out which brand of soap is mostly preferred by the consumers and why they choose a particular soap. The researcher wants to analyze by understanding micro level study in Mayiladuthurai town.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To analyze the most popular washing soap
- To study the various factors determining the brand preference of the washing soap.
- To identify the impact on advertisement of washing soap in the study area.
- To identify the findings and offer suitable suggestions.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

In order to know the details about customers taste and preference of various detergents in Mayiladuthurai town. This study makes an attempt to analyze the various factors influencing a consumer while purchasing of quality detergent cake i.e., the knowledge of consumers about the various products attributes like price, quality, package, etc., and also to know the reason for brand preference.

METHODOLOGY

An intensive study has been made on the consumer preference of washing soap users in Mayiladuthurai. The methodology adopted in the collection and analysis of data detailed below.

SOURCES OF DATA

To analyze the consumer brand preference of washing soap, both primary and secondary data were used. Primary data were collected through an interview schedule and by detailed discussions with respondent. Secondary data was collected from the various books, journals, newspapers and websites.

SAMPLING

By adapting convenient sampling technique, 150 respondents were chosen from among the population in Mayiladuthurai town.

COLLECTION OF DATA

A well structured interview schedule was prepared for the purpose of data collection. The interview schedule includes personal back ground information of the consumer, preference of consumers towards a particular brand of washing soap, purchasing pattern, reasons for usage, place of purchase, media influence on the respondent.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

The following table shows the demographics of the respondents for the survey. The collected data were subjected to statistical analysis. Simple percentages were used for analyzed the data.

Table-1 Demographic variable

Particulars	Classification	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	46	31
	Female	104	69
Age	18-25	37	25
	26-35	46	31
	36-45	22	14
	46-50	25	17
	Above 51 years	20	13
Educational level	No formal education	20	13
	school	28	19
	UG	54	36
	PG	31	21
	Above PG	17	11
Monthly Income	Below 15,000	52	35
	15,000-25,000	43	29
	25000-35,000	35	23
	Above 35,000	20	13

Source: Primary Data

From the above table-1 it is inferred that majority of the respondents (69%) are female and belong to the age group of 26-35(31%) and 36% of the respondents have completed their higher education and earn monthly income below Rs.15,000 (35%).

Table 2 Brand preference of the respondents

Name of the brand	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Rin	35	23
Power	20	14
Arasan	14	9
Wheel	10	7
Surf Excel	25	17
Tide	9	6
Henko	8	5
Mr.white	11	8
Oorvasi	6	4
Ponvand	8	5
Others	3	2
Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 2 shows various brands of washing soap used by the consumer. Through the table Rin soap possessed 23% of the respondent as a highest in the rank then surf excel 17% power 14% and so on.

Table 3 Factor consider for brand preference of washing soap

Factors	No. of respondents	Percentage
Quality	84	40
Price	23	30
Advertisement	30	20
Special offer	13	10
Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table 3.9 shows that factor consider for brand preference of washing soap. 40% of the sample respondent have expressed their view quality is the main factor, 30% of the respondent have mentioned consumer preference depends upon the price of the brand, 20% were represent mainly depends upon the advertisement and 10% of them have represent were special offer.

Table-4 Level of satisfaction of brand preference

Level of satisfaction	No. of respondents	Percentage
Very high	16	10
High	93	62
Normal	33	22
Low	5	2
Very Low	3	4
Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table 4 shows, the satisfactory level of the respondents exhibited. The highest score is given to the high of satisfaction i.e., 62%, whereas 22% of the respondents are come under the category of the normal, 10% of the respondents represent have level of satisfaction is very high.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study is limited in Mayiladuthurai town only and 150 respondents have been approached with the interview schedule among the large number of washing soap users. The finds are drawn only on the basis of inferences made in the study. Therefore the validity of findings is subject to the true information provided by the consumer on washing soap.

FINDINGS

1. The gender wise classification of the washing soap users in the study area, out of 150 respondents, 46 of them belong to the male category and remaining 104 of the respondents belongs to female category.

2. The Rin soap occupies a major share of the market place i.e., 32 percentage due
3. to provide high quality, reasonable price and various size depends upon the consumer taste and satisfaction.
4. It is seen from the above analysis more than $3/4^{\text{th}}$ of the respondents are not change the usual brand of the soap.
5. It is found that majority of the respondent considered the quality of washing soap in a particular brand.
6. It is seen from the above analysis $1/3^{\text{rd}}$ of the respondents are represent buying the soap from small retailer shop.
7. From the analysis, most of the respondent highly satisfied with particular brand of soap.
8. It is clearly concluded that nearly half of the respondents says advertisement is to motivate to buying the soap.

SUGGESTIONS

Based on the views obtained from the respondents and relevant analysis made in the study the following suggestions are made for further improvement of the marketing strategies adopted by the producers of washing soap.

1. As a detergent soap manufacturing companies always maintain quality improvement should be seriously considered.
2. Soap manufacturing companies supply the soap in the market at reasonable rate and consumer taste and preference.
3. If any complaint from the washing soap the marketers should take necessary action and solve the problems.
4. Necessary sales promotion schemes should be introduced at frequent intervals.
5. Washing soap manufacturing companies are provide discount, quantity offer and free gift on behalf of the expectation of consumers.
6. Manufactures should improve the brand images, improving service standards and increasing number of product.

7. Price of some of the brands of soaps should be reduced and also mainly focus on the customer relationship.

CONCLUSION

The market for washing soap is becoming more competitive now a day. Therefore, the producer of detergent soap should understand consumer preference much to find higher sales of their product. A consumer prefers a particular brand based on what benefits that brand can offer. The brand selection of the consumers depends on the needs in case of the washing soap as consumers use different brands for different types of cloth. In this study, it was observed that in forming tendency of consumers to prefer a particular brand, the variable such as price, quality, Advertisement, special offer etc., play an essential role. The marketer's needs to understand above variables of brand to develop in washing soaps as a multi utility of detergent soap. All in one is the need of consumer.

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